

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE PYRAZOLES*

Sl. no.**	R ₁	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅	60	82
2.	2-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₅	65	155
3.	4-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₅	62	120
4.	2-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅	62	195
5.	3-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅	60	180
6.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅	55	195
7.	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₅	55	165
8.	4-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	62	140
9.	2-NO ₂ , 4-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅	60	150
10.	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	65	120
11.	2-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	150
12.	4-CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	154
13.	2-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	55	200
14.	3-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	201
15.	4-NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	58	230
16.	2-OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	60	140
17.	3-Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl ₂	65	140
18.	4-Br	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ ClBr	65	180
19.	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₄	55	126
20.	2-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄	50	135
21.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄	50	150
22.	2-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₆	52	160
23.	3-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₆	54	195
24.	4-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₆	50	178
25.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆	52	119
26.	3-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	50	112
27.	4-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	50	135
28.	2-NO ₂ , 4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆	52	136
29.	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	55	108
30.	2-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	50	138
31.	4-CH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₄ Cl	52	130
32.	2-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₆ Cl	50	188
33.	3-NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₆ Cl	50	160
34.	2-OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₆ Cl	55	132
35.	3-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₄ Cl ₂	54	130
36.	4-Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₄ Cl ₂	50	160
37.	4-Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₄ ClBr	50	170
38.	2-NO ₂ , 4-Cl	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₈ O ₅ Cl ₂	52	200

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

**For compounds sl. nos. 1-9, R₂=H, R₃=-C(=NH).NH₂.HNO₂; for sl. nos. 10-18, R₂=2-Cl, R₃=-C(=NH).NH₂.HNO₂; for sl. nos. 19-28, R₂=H, R₃=2,4-DNP; for sl. nos. 29-38, R₂=2-Cl, R₃=2,4-DNP.

The ir spectra also support the above structures. The presence of the CO stretching band at 1 570-1 640 cm⁻¹ instead of the normal conjugated ketones (1 650-1 720 cm⁻¹) may be due to reduction of the double bond character by resonance between two structures. Furthermore, shifting of the acetyl CO to 1 665 cm⁻¹ instead of 1 720 cm⁻¹ indicates the effect of conjugation of CO with a C=N double bond. The stretching bands at 1 690-1 500 cm⁻¹ probably result from the second conjugated CO involved in hydrogen bonding. In addition the large shift and broadening of the NH stretching band at 3 110-3 220 cm⁻¹ and the shift and reduction of the second CO stretching band can only result from a strong hydrogen bonding as shown in the above structures. The hydrazono structure to similar type of compounds has also been assigned by others^{2,3}.

1-Guanyl (2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-3-phenylamino-5-methyl-4-arylazopyrazoles; To 2-arylhydrazono-1-

phenylaminobutane-1,3-dione (0.001 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (10-15 ml), was added to a solution of aminoguanidine nitrate/2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.001 mol) in acetic acid (10-15 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool overnight and the resulting crystals were recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 82° (Found: N, 29.16; C, 53.49. C₁₇H₁₅N₅O₅ calcd. for: N, 29.31; C, 52.40%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 244, 251 and 370 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 590 (-N=N), 1 620 (-C=N- or -C=C-), 3 120 and 750 cm⁻¹ (phenyl); δ (CDCl₃) 2.76 (3H, CH₃), 8.87 (H, NHC₆H₅), 11.37 (2H, NH₂) and 7.1-7.8 (10-ArH).

The physical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

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[1,2,4]Triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino-[5,6-c]cinnolin-9-one

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IN continuation of our work to synthesise heterocyclics by new routes, an attempt has been made to synthesise 10-methyl-11H,13H-[1,2,4]triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-c]cinnolin-11-one (3a; R=R'=H) by refluxing equimolar quantities of 3-bromo-4-hydroxycinnoline (2) with 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (1). But both the reactants were recovered in

quantitative yield. The reaction did not succeed even by heating a neat mixture of both the reactants at 160–70°, showing the inertness of bromine at C₈ and hydroxy at C₄ of **2**. However, 3,4-dichlorocinnoline (**4a**; R=R'=H) condensed smoothly with **1** and the product gave positive test for sulphur and negative test for halogen, thereby indicating that both the halogens attached to C₈ and C₄ of cinnoline have reacted giving rise to ring-closed compound.

Close scrutiny would reveal that the reaction of **1** and **4a** (R=R'=H) could lead to the formation of **3a** (R=R'=H) and 10-methyl-7H,9H[1,2,4]-triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-c]cinnolin-9-one (**5a**; R=R'=H) or both. But in our case one product was formed to which we have assigned structure **5a** (R=R'=H) on the basis that in cinnoline nucleus, bromine attached to C₈ is comparatively less reactive as shown by the inertness of **2** to react with **1**. Secondly, survey of literature^{1,2} revealed that chlorine attached to C₄ is very reactive.

The pmr spectra (CDCl₃+TFA) of **5a** (R=R'=H) showed a singlet (3H) at δ 2.70 assignable to three protons of the methyl group at position-10. Besides, it exhibited a multiplet (4H) at δ 7.37–8.30 assignable to four aromatic protons. The single proton attached to nitrogen did not appear due to the presence of TFA.

Structure **5a** (R=R'=H) finds further support from the fact that the mercapto group of 2-aminothiophenol reacted with 4-chloroquinazoline in preference to amino group as reported earlier³.

Further, it was considered worthwhile to introduce methoxy groups at positions 2 and 3 of this system by the condensation of **1** with 3,4-dichloro-6,7-dimethoxycinnoline (**4b**; R=R'=OCH₃) in ethanol, but both the reactants were recovered quantitatively. The reaction did not succeed even by heating the reactants at 160–70°.

The reactivity of chlorine attached to C₄ is due to the basic nature of N₁ of cinnoline (**6**). But Castle and Cox⁴ reported that in case of 4-chloro-6,7-dimethoxycinnoline, the reactivity of chlorine towards nucleophilic attack at C₄ is reduced. According to their view, the methoxy group at C₈ of the cinnoline ring can inhibit in part the normal shift in the hetero ring of cinnoline by contributing electrons along a conjugated path to the C₄. The methoxy group at C₇ should have no marked influence upon the C₄ as shown in structures **7a** and **7b**.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes in a liquid paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Pmr spectrum was recorded on a Varian EM-390 90MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Scheme 1

Attempted condensation of 3-bromo-4-hydroxycinnoline (2) with 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro[1,2,4]triazine (1). Method A: A solution of **2**⁵ (0.225 g, 0.001 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was mixed with a solution of **1**⁶ (0.158 g, 0.001 mol) in the same solvent (10 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 10 h. No reaction took place and both the reactants were recovered as such.

Method B: A mixture of **2** (0.001 mol) and **1** (0.001 mol) in a dry test tube was heated in an oil bath at 160–70° for 5 h. No reaction took place and the reactants were again recovered as such.

10-Methyl-7H,9H[1,2,4]triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-c]cinnolin-9-one (5a; R=R'=H): To a solution of **1** (0.316 g, 0.002 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added a solution of 3,4-dichlorocinnoline⁷ (**4a**, R=R'=H; 0.398 g, 0.002 mol) in the same solvent (20 ml). To it was added fused sodium acetate (0.345 g, 0.004 mol) and the contents were refluxed over a steam-bath for 6 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was collected under suction, washed with water and crystallised from dioxan to a dark brown product (0.28 g, 49%), m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 50.86; H, 2.93; N, 29.45. C₁₂H₈N₆OS calcd. for: C, 50.70; H, 2.82; N, 29.58%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 180, 1 672, 1 600, 1 520, 1 460, 1 378, 1 292, 1 160, 1 080, 1 028 and 870 cm⁻¹; δ (TFA) 2.70 (3H, s, CH₃) and 7.37–8.30 (4H, m, ArH).

Attempted synthesis of 2,3-dimethoxy-10-methyl-7H,9H[1,2,4]triazino[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-c]cinnolin-9-one (5b; R=R'=OCH₃). Method A: Equimolar quantities of **4b** (R=R'=OCH₃)⁸ and **1** were refluxed in ethanol for 8 h in the presence

of fused sodium acetate. No reaction took place and both the reactants were recovered as such.

Method B: A mixture of **4b** ($R=R'=OCH_3$; 0.259 g, 0.001 mol) and **1** (0.158 g, 0.001 mol) in a dry test tube was heated in an oil-bath at $160-70^\circ$ for 4 h. No reaction took place and the reactants were recovered as such.

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Studies on Thiazolidinone. Part-XVIII. Synthesis of Thiazolidinone Derivatives from Benzosuberone and Cyclohexanone

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IN continuation of our earlier work on thiazolidinone derivatives¹ as potential chemotherapeutic agents, the synthesis of two new series of thiazolidinones possessing alicyclic moieties as a part of the substituent have been made. 2-Amino-4-aryl-cyclohexa[1,2-d]pyrimidines (**1a**) were obtained in 50–80% yield by the reaction of free guanidine on 2-arylidene cyclohexanones by following the procedure reported for the synthesis of **1b**^{2,3}. The amines (**1a** and **1b**) were smoothly converted into unsymmetrical thioureas (**2a** and **2b**) by reacting them with phenylisothiocyanate in rectified spirit. The condensation of monochloroacetic acid with thioureas furnished the thiazolidinones, the structures of which are confirmed as **3a** and **3b** since the hydrolysis of these compounds in alcoholic HCl gave 3-phenyl-2,4-thiazolidione in all cases along

with the respective amines (**2**). The thiazolidinones are highly soluble in dilute NaOH and reprecipitated by acetic acid. The ir spectra of the thiazolidinones (**3a** and **3b**; $Ar=C_6H_5$) showed bands at 1710 and 1700 cm^{-1} for the carbonyl groups whereas their benzylidene derivatives (**4a** and **4b**; $Ar=C_6H_5$) gave bands at 1670 and 1675 cm^{-1} respectively for their carbonyl groups. This is in good agreement with our earlier observation⁴, with other series of compounds. The bathochromic shifts in the absorption of carbonyl group are due to exocyclic conjugation⁵.

Scheme 1 Reagents : (i) C_6H_5NCS , EtOH, Δ , (ii) $ClCH_2COOH$, NaOAc, AcOH, (iii) C_6H_5CHO , AcOH, NaOAc

Experimental

Melting points are determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

2-Amino-4-aryl-benzo[6,7]cyclohepta[1,2-d]pyrimidines (**1b**) were prepared according to Rayyes, *et al.*³ by the reaction of 2-arylidene benzosuberones with guanidine carbonate and 2-arylidene cyclohexanones were synthesised by condensing cyclohexanone with aldehydes in alkali⁶.

2-Amino-4-phenyl-cyclohexa[1,2-d]pyrimidine (1a; $Ar=C_6H_5$): To a solution of guanidine hydrochloride (3.6 g, 40 mmol) in ethanol (60 ml) was added a solution of NaOH (4 g in 100 ml of water) and stirred for 30 min. The precipitated NaCl was filtered off. The filtrate was added to a solution of 2-benzylidene cyclohexanone (1.9 g, 10 mmol) in ethanol (50 ml) and refluxed for 4 h. Excess solvent was then distilled off and the residue treated with water and warmed to make it soluble. The aqueous solution after filtration was acidified with dilute HCl (0.1N). The resulting solid was filtered, washed with warm ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol as a pale yellow solid (2.1 g, 65%), m.p. 186°